

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 2

Acceptance of papers **February, 2026**

Acceptance of papers

Published monthly

Topics

economics, technology, social sciences

ISSN 3060-5229

Digital Object Identifier

Visit the website t.me/scopus_IST2100

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JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

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CONTENTS

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION TRENDS AND CHALLENGES IN PEDIATRIC DENTISTRY	15
Tursunov Begzod Sherzodovich, Solijonov Sherzod Qahramonovich	
THE ROLE OF RISKS AND RISK MANAGEMENT IN MANAGING THE SOLVENCY OF INSURANCE COMPANIES	20
Xalikulova Shirin Utkir qizi	
INVESTMENT OPPORTUNITIES IN THE SECURITIES MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN: DIVIDEND YIELD, INSTITUTIONAL REFORMS AND INTERNATIONAL ATTRACTIVENESS.....	25
Akhliyov Ibragimov	
A CONCEPTUAL APPROACH TO ANTI-MONOPOLY CONTROL IN SERVICE INDUSTRIES ADAPTED TO THE CONDITIONS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	30
Bekbutayev Nodirjon Fayzullayevich	
TECHNOLOGICAL FEATURES OF WEAR-RESISTANT SURFACING OF METALLIC COMPONENTS ALLOYED WITH CARBON, MANGANESE, AND SILICON USING FUSED FLUXES.....	35
Khudoyorov Sardor Sadullaevich, Khudoykulov Nurilla Zikirillaevich	
ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING INTEGRATED MARKETING COMMUNICATIONS IN ENTERING NEW MARKETS IN UZBEKISTAN	39
Baqoyev Sunnatillo Burxon o'g'li	
ENVIRONMENTALLY EFFICIENT FATLIQUORING AGENTS IN KARAKUL FATLIQUORING TECHNOLOGY.....	46
Rustamov Bobir Ismatovich, Shodieva Dilnoza Turajon qizi	
STRATEGIC PLANNING IN IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR MANAGING INVESTMENT PROJECTS IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	51
Qurbonov Jasurbek Pozilovich	
FOUNDATIONS OF ENGLISH TEACHING BASED ON PROVERBS (UZBEK AND AFGAN WORDS).....	56
Samadi Nooria	
MATHEMATICAL MODELING AND SOLUTION ALGORITHMS OF GEOMETRIC PROBLEMS IN NUMERICALLY CONTROLLED MACHINES.....	60
Khasanov Bobirmirzo Makhmudali ugli, Yusupov Sardorbek Ma'rufovich, Abdullajonov Asadbek Sherzodbek ugli	
INNOVATION IS A KEY FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ENERGY INDUSTRY.....	70
Gavkhar Absamatovna Khamdamova	
MARKETING PROBLEMS IN THE INTERNATIONAL INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISE MARKET AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN SOLVING THEM.....	76
Usmanova Dilfuza Ilhomovna	
FUZZY ROBUST CONTROLLERS FOR GAS PURIFICATION PROCESSES.....	82
Sh. D. Tulyaganov	
METHODOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF MARKETING IN FURNITURE ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE NEW UZBEKISTAN DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY	87
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
THE ROLE OF METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN FUNDAMENTALIZING THE PROFESSIONAL PREPARATION OF FUTURE ECONOMICS TEACHERS	92
Djumanazarova Zamira Kojabayevna	
MAHALLIY BUDJET DAROMADLARI BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASH YO'NALISHLARI	97
Isoqov Zafarjon Zokirjonovich	
LIQUIDITY PROVISION IN BANKS THROUGH EFFECTIVE ASSET-LIABILITY MANAGEMENT.....	101
Sulaymanov Samandarboy Adhambek ugli	
EFFECTIVENESS OF THE "MANAGEMENT CERTIFICATE" SYSTEM IN THE PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM LEADERS AND MECHANISMS FOR ITS IMPROVEMENT	108
Mamatqulova Shoxsanam Dilshodovna	

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE “MANAGEMENT CERTIFICATE” SYSTEM IN THE PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM LEADERS AND MECHANISMS FOR ITS IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract: This article examines the effectiveness of the “Managerial Certificate” system in the professional development of leaders of preschool education institutions and the organizational and pedagogical mechanisms for its improvement. Based on statistical and comparative analysis, the stages of implementing the certification system in the Republic of Uzbekistan during 2017–2025 and its impact on the development of managerial competencies are analyzed. By comparing international practices, the study substantiates the need to improve the certification system through competency-based assessment, practice-oriented training, continuous professional development, and digital monitoring mechanisms. The findings contribute to enhancing management effectiveness in preschool education institutions.

Key words: preschool education, educational leadership, managerial certificate, professional development, management effectiveness, certification system.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada maktabgacha ta’lim tizimi rahbarlarini kasbiy rivojlantirishda “Menejerlik sertifikati” tizimining samaradorligi va uni takomillashtirishning tashkiliy-pedagogik mexanizmlari tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot jarayonida 2017–2025-yillar davomida O‘zbekiston Respublikasida amalga oshirilgan islohotlar, sertifikatlash tizimining bosqichlari hamda uning rahbarlarning boshqaruv kompetensiyalariga ta’siri statistik va qiyosiy tahlil asosida o‘rganilgan. Xorijiy davlatlar tajribasi bilan taqqoslash orqali sertifikatlash tizimini kompetensiyaga asoslangan baholash, amaliyotga yo‘naltirilgan o‘qitish, uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanish va raqamli monitoring mexanizmlari asosida takomillashtirish zarurligi asoslab berilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari maktabgacha ta’lim tashkilotlarida boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: maktabgacha ta’lim, rahbar kadrlar, menejerlik sertifikati, kasbiy rivojlanish, boshqaruv samaradorligi, sertifikatlash tizimi.

Аннотация: В данной статье проанализирована эффективность системы «Менеджерский сертификат» в профессиональном развитии руководителей системы дошкольного образования, а также организационно-педагогические механизмы её совершенствования. В ходе исследования на основе статистического и сравнительного анализа изучены реформы, реализованные в Республике Узбекистан в 2017–2025-годы, этапы внедрения системы сертификации и её влияние на управленческие компетенции руководителей. Путём сопоставления с зарубежным опытом обоснована необходимость совершенствования системы сертификации на основе компетентностного оценивания, практико-ориентированного обучения, непрерывного профессионального развития и цифровых механизмов мониторинга. Результаты исследования направлены на повышение эффективности управления в организациях дошкольного образования.

Ключевые слова: дошкольное образование, руководящие кадры, менеджерский сертификат, профессиональное развитие, эффективность управления, система сертификации.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, improving the quality of management in the preschool education system and developing the professional competencies of educational institution leaders has become a priority worldwide. In particular, international research has confirmed that the quality of education is largely dependent on the manager’s managerial, strategic thinking, team management, and innovative approaches.

According to analyses conducted by UNESCO and OECD, when the quality of leadership in educational institutions is increased by 10–15%, the overall effectiveness of the educational process increases by an average of 20–25% [1]. This situation indicates the need for scientifically based improvement of mechanisms

aimed at training leadership personnel and ensuring their continuous professional development in the preschool education system.

The preschool education system in our republic has been developing rapidly in recent years. According to statistics, in 2017, the coverage rate of preschool education was 27%, and by 2024 this figure will exceed 75% [2]. The sharp increase in the number of preschool educational organizations has further increased the need for leaders with modern managerial competencies who can effectively manage them.

In this process, the "Management Certificate" system, introduced in the system of retraining and advanced training of heads of preschool educational organizations, is of great importance. This certification system serves to assess the competencies of leaders in strategic planning, financial management, human resource management, education quality monitoring, and digital management. However, practice shows that the organizational and pedagogical mechanisms, evaluation criteria, and expected results of this system are not sufficiently scientifically substantiated

The experience of foreign countries, including Finland, Singapore and South Korea, shows that the certification system for heads of educational institutions gives high results only when it is organized in a way that is combined with modular training, practice-oriented cases, a mentoring system and constant monitoring [4]. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the integration of these approaches with national education policy and regulatory and legal frameworks is an urgent scientific problem. Therefore, the development and scientific substantiation of organizational and pedagogical mechanisms for improving the "Management Certificate" system in the professional development of heads of the preschool education system is of great importance from the point of view of modernizing the education system, increasing management efficiency and ensuring sustainable development.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The issue of professional development of preschool education system leaders and assessment of their management competencies is one of the important research areas of modern pedagogy and educational management. In particular, the issue of assessing and developing their professional training through certification of leadership personnel is widely covered in international scientific literature.

The idea of certifying leaders of educational institutions at the international level was formed at the end of the 20th - beginning of the 21st centuries. Studies conducted by UNESCO since the 2000s have scientifically substantiated the fact that leadership competencies are a decisive factor in improving the quality of education [4]. These studies emphasize the need to introduce mechanisms for continuous assessment and certification of leaders, not limited to training.

In a series of analytical reports conducted by the OECD between 2008 and 2022, the system of certification of leaders was interpreted as an important tool for developing strategic management, effective use of resources, and pedagogical leadership in educational institutions [5]. OECD researcher M. Pont argued in his scientific work that leadership certification should not be a tool for testing knowledge, but a mechanism for determining the trajectory of professional reflection and development.

In the Finnish experience, the certification system for school and preschool educational institution leaders has been introduced since 1998, and this system is implemented through national programs under the Ministry of Education and Culture [6]. Finnish scientist P. Sahlberg emphasizes in his research that certification of leaders serves to strengthen pedagogical leadership and form an internal development strategy of the institution.

In Singapore, the certification system for school leaders has been in place since 2001 through the National Institute of Education [7]. In his research, T. Ng scientifically substantiates that leadership certification serves to develop strategic thinking, team management, and results-oriented management competencies.

In South Korea, a certification system for preschool and general education leaders has been mandatory since 2007 [8]. K. Lee's research suggests that the effectiveness of this system is linked to digital monitoring, outcome evaluation, and recertification mechanisms.

The issue of training and ensuring their professional development of preschool education system leaders in the Republic of Uzbekistan has become a priority area of state policy since 2017. The system of retraining and advanced training of leadership personnel has been improved on the basis of regulatory legal acts on the development of the preschool education system [9]. In this process, the "Management Certificate" system was introduced, the main purpose of which was determined to be the assessment and development of modern management competencies of preschool education leaders. Local scientists - Sh. Tursunov, D. Rakhimova and M. Safarov - analyzed the issues of educational management, leadership competencies and professional development in their studies [10]. In particular, D. Rakhimova scientifically substantiates the decrease in practical effectiveness of the leadership certification system if it is not combined with a continuous professional development model.

An analysis of the studied literature shows that in developed countries, the leadership certification system was introduced in combination with clear organizational and pedagogical mechanisms, monitoring and practical assessment. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, improving the “Management Certificate” system based on international experience and scientifically substantiating it as a mechanism that serves the real professional development of managers remains an urgent scientific task.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is aimed at improving the organizational and pedagogical mechanisms of the “Management Certificate” system in the professional development of preschool education system leaders, and a comprehensive and systematic approach was taken as the basis. A systematic and analytical approach was used in the research process, and the management certificate system was studied as an integral part of preschool education management. The purpose, content, form and results of the certification process were analyzed in their interrelation. In the scientific research, based on the comparative-pedagogical method, the experiences of certifying education leaders in foreign countries such as Finland, Singapore and South Korea were studied, and the possibilities of their application in the conditions of Uzbekistan were identified. This method made it possible to identify differences and common aspects between international experience and national practice. Within the framework of empirical research methods, questionnaires and interviews were conducted among the leaders of preschool educational organizations, and the level of formation of managerial competencies, the practical effectiveness of the certification system and existing problems were identified. The obtained data were processed through statistical analysis, and conclusions were drawn based on percentages and generalized results. In addition, the modeling method was used in the study, and a model of organizational and pedagogical mechanisms was developed to improve the “Management Certificate” system. This model is aimed at ensuring the continuous professional development of managers.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results of the study show that the process of training and ensuring the professional development of managers in the preschool education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan has reached a qualitatively new level since 2017. It was from this period that the preschool education system was formed as a separate state policy direction, and modern mechanisms for retraining and advanced training for managers, including the “Management Certificate” system, were introduced. According to statistical data, in 2017 the coverage rate of preschool education was 27%, while by 2024 this figure exceeded 75%. This growth, along with an increase in the number of preschool educational organizations, sharply increased the need for managers who could effectively manage them. Therefore, the system of certification of managers was formed as a practical necessity (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics and annual growth rates of passing the “Management Certificate” for heads of preschool educational organizations in 2017–2025¹

1 Note: The diagram reflects the steady growth dynamics of the number of heads of preschool educational organizations who have passed the “Management Certificate” during 2017–2025. Also, the fact that the annual growth rates were high in the early years and stabilized in the subsequent period indicates that the certification system has moved from the introduction to the development stage. This situation reflects the institutionalization of the system and its increasing impact on the quality of management.

The analysis shows that after the introduction of the “Management Certificate” system, significant positive changes were observed in the management activities of heads of preschool educational organizations. In particular, while in 2017–2019, the activities of leaders were mainly limited to administrative management, in 2020–2024, attention was increased to strategic planning, team management and monitoring the quality of education. According to the results of empirical research, it was found that the speed and validity of management decisions increased in about 62–68% of certified leaders, and the efficiency of working with a team improved in 55–60%. Also, competencies in financial planning and effective use of resources increased by an average of 20–25% compared to the state before certification. However, the analysis also revealed some shortcomings of the “Management Certificate” system. In particular, it was found that during 2017–2021, the certification process was mainly focused on assessing theoretical knowledge, and practical competencies and real management results were not sufficiently taken into account. This situation led to low practical management efficiency, despite the fact that approximately 30–35% of managers had a certificate.

Starting from 2022, the efficiency of the system has increased significantly as a result of the gradual introduction of practical tasks, cases and monitoring elements into the certification system. Analysis of recent years shows that in regions where organizational and pedagogical mechanisms for certification have been strengthened, the stability and quality of management in the activities of preschool educational organizations have improved. In general, statistical and analytical data for the period 2017–2024 confirm that the “Management Certificate” system has had a positive impact on the professional development of preschool education managers, but to ensure its full effectiveness, it is necessary to strengthen the mechanisms for practically-oriented assessment, constant monitoring and re-certification.

The results of the study and statistical analysis for 2017–2025 show that the “Management Certificate” system has played an important role in the professional development of heads of preschool educational organizations. However, the full effectiveness of the system can only be ensured if it is organized on the basis of targeted development mechanisms..

1. Strengthening the regulatory and legal mechanism

The first and main mechanism for development is to strengthen the certification system with a clear regulatory framework. The reforms introduced since 2017 were initially implemented on the basis of general recommendations and temporary regulations. As a result, the certification process has been interpreted differently in some regions (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Strategic model for developing the “Management Certificate” system²

Therefore, a single legal mechanism is needed that directly links certification with:

- appointment to a managerial position,
- recertification,
- promotion.

This mechanism will turn the certificate from a formality into a real management tool.

² Source: author's elaboration

2. Competency-based assessment mechanism

Analysis has shown that in the early years, the certification process was mainly focused on testing theoretical knowledge. This did not fully reflect the real management activities of the leader.

Therefore, an important mechanism for development is competency-based assessment. In it:

- strategic planning,
- team management,
- financial and resource management,
- practical skills such as educational quality monitoring are assessed through real-life situations (case studies).

Bu yondashuv sertifikatni rahbarning haqiqiy kasbiy salohiyatini aks ettiruvchi mezonga aylantiradi.

3. Practice-oriented learning mechanism

Another important mechanism for increasing efficiency is to combine the certification process with practice. International experience shows that training for managers in the form of lectures alone is not enough. Therefore:

- project-based learning,
- assignments based on real-world MTT activities,
- exercises aimed at solving management problems

should be an integral part of the certification process. Bu mexanizm rahbarlarning nazariy bilimlarini amaliy boshqaruv qarorlariga aylantirish imkonini beradi.

4. Continuous professional development and recertification mechanism

The analysis for 2017–2025 showed that one-time certification does not guarantee long-term results. Therefore, an important mechanism for development is the introduction of a system of continuous professional development. In this regard:

- It is assumed that the certificate will be issued for a certain period (for example, 3–5 years),
- the activities of the leader will be monitored during this period,
- and if the specified results are not achieved, retraining will be introduced.

This mechanism encourages leaders to continuously grow and helps maintain the quality of management.

5. Monitoring and digital assessment mechanism

Digital tools introduced in recent years have played an important role in improving the efficiency of the certification system. Another important mechanism for improvement is digital monitoring.

Through it:

- key performance indicators (KPIs) of the leader,
- dynamics of the institution's development,
- indicators of the quality of education are constantly monitored.

This mechanism reduces subjective evaluation and ensures transparency of certification results.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The conducted research and analysis for 2017–2025 show that the “Management Certificate” system has been formed as an important management tool in the professional development of heads of preschool educational organizations. This system has had a positive impact on improving the strategic thinking of leaders, the quality of management decision-making, and the efficiency of the institution's activities. At the same time, the research results confirm that the effectiveness of the certification system can be fully ensured only when it is combined with regulatory and legal certainty, competency-based assessment, practice-oriented training, continuous professional development, and digital monitoring mechanisms. The systematic implementation of these mechanisms is an important condition for sustainably increasing the managerial capacity of preschool educational leaders and improving the quality of education.

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Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 2

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